

BrainGear: Learning to drive a BMI based intelligent wheelchair

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Abstract—Brain-machine interfaces (BMIs) are systems able to translate human brain patterns into commands for robotic devices. Despite the flourishing of brain-actuated prototypes, after three decades of research, BMI is still lacking practicable solutions for daily use by end-users. Current research approaches that assume that BMI should be treated only as a decoder tool, have not been able to face this translational challenge. *BrainGear* (a two-year project, funded by the Dept. of Information Engineering of the University of Padova) radically revolutionizes the traditional approach by reformulating BMI as a multifaceted symbiotic learning entity where the three actors involved —user, decoder, and robotic device— have to mutually learn from each other. Neuroscientific and robotic methodologies are combined in order to create and explicitly promote the mutual learning interactions between each of these actors.

Index Terms—brain-machine interface, powered wheelchair, learning, neurorobotics

I. INTRODUCTION

The possibility to directly decode user's intentions from brain signals by circumventing the damaged neural pathways has highlighted the potential of Brain-Machine Interfaces (BMIs) as assistive tools for restoring the independence of people suffering from severe motor disabilities [1], re-enabling communication capabilities [2], and even for substituting lost motor functions [3]. Traditionally, a BMI system interprets and translates user's brain patterns into commands for the external device. Based on this classic approach, researchers have prototyped a variety of brain-actuated robotic solutions ranging from mobile robots for telepresence to robotic arms for manipulation and powered wheelchairs for navigation [4]. The goal has always been the same: to demonstrate the feasibility of BMI as assistive technology. However, despite these technological and methodological advances, evidence of daily usage of BMI systems is currently scarce and only few BMI applications have been reported to be independently employed by end-users at home and for long periods of time [5]. To date, after 30 years of research, most BMI technology is still restricted to laboratory research and its translational potentials have not yet been fulfilled.

The reason for this is threefold: first, the reliability of BMI is not guaranteed for every potential user due to the intrinsic non-stationarity of neural signals. As a consequence, users may experience extreme variability in day-to-day performances or may even not be able to reach a sufficient level of BMI control. Second, BMI efficiency is strongly limited by ineffective

Fig. 1. The intelligent wheelchair prototype developed in BrainGear

training strategies where users are asked to perform repetitive and artificial mental tasks to calibrate the decoder that do not refer to any real daily activity. Third, the usability of BMI-driven devices is still questionable: indeed, the integration of BMI and robotics is still at its infancy and, definitely not fully explored. As a consequence, most BMI-driven robotic devices can execute only simple actions and, in general, are seen only as mere actuators of the user's command. Traditionally, the most common approach has been limited to investigate techniques to improve the reliability of the BMI decoder and, indirectly, the other two aforementioned limitations. The underlying hypothesis—that quickly became a widely accepted axiom—is that BMI should be exclusively considered as a decoding tool. Therefore, researchers have mainly been committed to propose new methodologies to process brain signals (and to increase, for instance, the signal-to-noise ratio) and/or to develop advanced machine learning algorithms to improve the number of possible commands and the BMI decoding accuracy. Most of the BMI works in the latest years have been focused on these topics. However, this univocal approach to BMIs has not been able to solve the aforementioned limitations, relegating brain interfaces to research laboratories as an intriguing—but unusable—technology.

II. PROJECT'S OVERVIEW

The primary aim of the project is to radically depart from the traditional approaches by fully reformulating BMI as a learning entity formed by the three actors that interact in

Fig. 2. The BMI as a threefold symbiotic learning system that takes into account the mutual interactions between user, decoder, and intelligent robot.

the system: the user, the decoder, and the intelligent robotic device (Figure 2). We postulate that these three actors need to mutually learn from each other in order to achieve successful BMI operations. To confirm the validity of this paradigm shift, it is necessary to verify the existence and demonstrate the benefits that the promotion of these learning interactions will have for brain-actuated devices. To this end, we are pursuing three objectives, one for each interaction, investigated in an experimental scenario based on a brain-driven powered wheelchair.

A. Objective O1: user-decoder interaction

The target of this objective is based on the idea that the system must support the user in understanding how to generate optimal neural patterns to control the BMI while, at the same time, adapting the decoder to properly follow the user’s learning curve. To this end, we posed a strong hypothesis: learning is not encoded and cannot be modeled in the input space generated by the features that are traditionally exploited in BMI systems (e.g., EEG amplitude). It should rather be investigated in an abstract, learning-correlated hyperspace where the acquired neural signals have been conveniently projected. The new learning neural correlates will be investigated by exploiting advanced techniques (e.g., neural manifold-based approaches) to project EEG features in new hyperspaces able to better track the user’s learning curve.

B. Objective O2: decoder-robot interaction

In the learning interaction between decoder and intelligent robotic device, the idea is to combine environmental information acquired by the robot sensors and the output of the BMI decoder in order to make the decoder learn (re-calibrate) based on the environment information. In several situations, the robot can autonomously predict what the most suitable action to-be-taken is (e.g., a forced turn to the left due to the structure of the environment). This prediction will be fed back to the BMI decoder and translated into probabilistic class-labels related to the mental tasks the user is performing. Then, the decoder will exploit these labels in order to re-calibrate itself. This new interaction modality will boost the reliability

and robustness of the BMI and promote the usability of brain-actuated robotic devices. We are using Bayesian probabilistic control approaches, semantic information, and dynamic system algorithms to this aim.

C. Objective O3: robot-user interaction

The third objective aims at exploiting the intelligence of the robot to guide the user during the training period. The robotic device takes the role of guide by instructing the user about the mental task to-be-performed, according to the concurrent operations and by gradually reducing the level of assistance while the user starts mastering the task. This will be achieved by defining new artificial intelligence algorithms based on dynamic game difficulty balancing where parameters and behaviors of the robot coherently change according to the BMI user skills. The goal is to provide an adaptive robotic learning system specifically tailored for the concurrent user’s needs.

D. Assessment

The project conceives a longitudinal evaluation in order to highlight the promotion of learning correlates for each of the three actors involved (i.e., subject, decoder and robotic device). In the experiments participants are asked to mentally drive the intelligent wheelchair in ecological situations. At least 10 healthy subjects and 10 tetraplegic end-users (spinal-cord injury, ASIA A) will be involved in the assessment phase.

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